

Management

SURVEY ON CONSUMER USER SATISFACTION THROUGH 5G NETWORK MEDICAL SYSTEM

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Abstract

This study focuses on the design of the 5G telemedicine monitoring platform. We use a questionnaire survey to investigate the patient's perception of the system. We found and explored some of the patients in the rural areas, patients with mobility problems to the hospital, to solve their problems and convenience. The results show that the 5G telemedicine monitoring system is established to build the interaction and monitoring benefits for the hospital and patients, and further to achieve its monitoring goals and treatment.

Keywords: 5G Telemedicine Monitoring Platform; Convenience; Interaction; Treatment.

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1. Introduction

In 2018, big data has become an important basis for forecasting and decision-making. The continuous innovation of Internet technology has become a way for the medical system, and the traditional medical treatment has brought about various new changes. In the past ten years, the types of medical consultations have been varied. For example, we use WeChat to make appointments for medical consultations and remote consultation with mobile APPs, so that long-distance consultation doctors can become a general direction for future medical treatment. In recent years, there have been many ways to see a doctor, such as online appointments and mobile phone consultation. Remote consultation is a direction. The network's consultation and treatment can often bring a lot of convenience, save patients' time, and can quickly infer what the patient is. Some patients do not want to tell the doctor face to face, and can also consult remotely through APP. Even some consultation software with online booking function is very convenient for patients. However, some doctors do not understand the overall situation of the customer. At this time, the doctor's reply may mislead the patient. There may be doctor-patient problems. Even many patients use the consultation platform as a one-off reference. A long-term medical platform has led to a very high rate of user churn in this area. On the other hand, 5G technology continues to innovate and progress. Many medical projects combine 5G technology. However, most of the 5G

technology applications are mostly based on clinical experiments and training. 5G medical care is not fully invested in the daily patient application level. On the one hand, China's medical resources are limited, and the actual age of the population is increasing. It is difficult to see a doctor and it is very cumbersome to see a doctor. Therefore, it is very practical to design a remote consultation platform by using 5G technology and medical collection. This article will focus on the existing 5G virtual technology, integrate it into the remote consultation platform, and design a remote consultation platform that fully utilizes 5G technology. This paper focuses on analyzing the current development of 5G medical technology at home and abroad, and research to achieve this. The theoretical basis of a platform, and provide relevant technical analysis, the end of this paper will provide a valuable feasibility program.

2. Literature Review

2.1. 5G Medical Electronic Loyalty

Consumer loyalty is a key factor in e-commerce platforms. Why consumers like to shop regularly on a certain platform, you can observe that consumers are happy with the trust and experience of a platform. The use and purchase of virtual experiences by many consumers online has also become the main direction of observation and analysis in this study. Dahl and Moreau (2007) mentioned that consumers participate in creation in three directions, namely, the experience of competence, the experience of autonomy, and the experience of hedonism. Through such a relationship, companies and consumers can create value together. The concept of creating value is often mentioned in the field of marketing management. The product style and quality provided by the manufacturer are ultimately aimed at creating the value of consumers. This series of processes is called value creation. We achieve consumer loyalty through information sharing on the platform and consumer recommendations. Evans (2015) suggests that consumer loyalty lies in continuous quality management and service management. Boakye et al, (2012) proposed that consumer loyalty is mainly to allow consumers to make decisions or services on products and to establish a relationship with each other. It can be seen that consumer loyalty mainly establishes the relationship between buyers and sellers. In many market marketing fields, relevant basic concepts are also mentioned. Through this concept, we can understand how the products and services provided by manufacturers can establish long-term. The partnership, this is a very important concept. Snipes, Loughman, and Fleck (2010) mention that the loss of a consumer can result in the loss of their company's finances. Therefore, consumer loyalty is a key factor for a company. Consumer electronic loyalty is mainly to establish the relationship between consumers and platforms. Balabanis (2006) mentions electronic loyalty as a platform needs to care about its consumer perception. McGuire (1974) refers to the theory of motivation, in which consumer perception influences the consumer's motivation to purchase. Therefore, we can clearly understand that the consumer's opportunity affects the subsequent purchase activities and further understand the electronic loyalty of its consumers. Gommans et al. (2001) mentioned that consumer loyalty encompasses the creation of consumer services and communities.

2.2. Co-Creating Value

McColl-Kennedy et al. (2017) mentioned the concept of creating value among consumers and producers. Understanding consumer intentions and loyalty allows manufacturers to create value.

Sweeney and Soutar (2001) refer to the concept of consumer value for the brand. From the price experience of the product, the value that the consumer wants can be obtained, which is equivalent to creating the value of the manufacturer and the consumer. Dahl and Moreau (2007) consumers will experience products and services through enjoyable shopping, and create value for manufacturers and consumers. Hoyer, Chandy, Dorotic, Krafft and Singh (2010) mention that co-creation allows companies to understand the needs of consumers and increase the competitiveness of their businesses. Fuller (2010) suggests that positive experiences can affect consumer trust, branding, and communication. Through this series of methods, you can build experience of creating value together. Creating value creates a long-term partnership between the company and the consumer, and through the value creation of both parties, it can continuously improve its cooperation.

2.3. Faith

Wang (2007) proposed that the trust of users will further become the belief of their consumers. Therefore, the increase in consumer trust will further become an individual's own belief. This research mainly hopes to understand the beliefs of its consumers through the quality of the platform. The quality and ease of use of platform design is also one of the most important factors. Consumer beliefs sometimes convey beliefs that affect other consumers, and these beliefs affect the beliefs of other different consumers. Zeithaml's (1988) mentions that consumer beliefs are primarily defined and judged by consumers about the quality of the product. Krosnick et al. (1993) mentioned that consumers' beliefs are selective and make the final decision based on consumer perception.

2.4. Trust

Morgan & Hunt (1994) pointed out that trust establishes the reliability and integrity of buyers and sellers.

Mayer et al. (1997) put forward the concept of trust, pointing out that the trust of both parties is to establish their relationship in an honest way. Trust is an important key factor for consumers. Mayer, Davis and Schoorman (1995) mentioned that in the process of trading, both parties are monitoring their behavior and believe that "talent", "goodwill" and "righteousness" are qualities of trust. In this APP station platform, it is necessary to establish trust in the consumer loyalty in advance, and the consumer's trust will be obtained by the consumer who is willing to purchase and apply again. Trust is mainly to establish a sense of trust between the platform and the consumer, whether it is the consumer's transaction, the consumer's data confidentiality, which will be the consumer's trust relationship. It can be seen that such a relationship establishment is very important and a long-term relationship.

2.5. Experience

Fornell (1992) proposed that the consumer experience is mainly in response to factors such as product quality and price, which affects consumer satisfaction. Our research focuses on the consumer experience of using and buying products online, and understanding their consumers' buying behavior. These commercial buying experience behaviors, we found that consumers will

pay attention to the reputation of their brands, let consumers decide whether to buy their products experience. Gruen, Osmonbekov, and Czaplewski (2006) suggest that consumer loyalty comes primarily from the consumer's experience and product quality, through which a process can create value. The multi-platform platform mainly provides consumers with more favorable prices than other competitors' platforms, and whether consumers jump from other platforms to their platforms.

2.6. Platform Design

The platform design is mainly to provide consumers with a safe use. Consumers can design their platforms through the ease of use and the look and feel of their platform design. The platform design includes the aesthetic perception, and the location of the platform products will attract consumers? These are all worthy of our discussion and research.

3. Research Method

The medical 5G platform website is mainly related to the relationship between the platform and the consumer. This study used a questionnaire survey to design its hypothesis. Our main architectural diagram is the contextual relationship to do its design and analysis. Kang, Morris, & Snell (2007) mentioned that trust relationships will become an important relationship partner in the operation of the platform, further generating its value. The five hypotheses designed in this study are:

- H1: Co-creation value is positively correlated with electronic loyalty
- H2: Faith has a positive correlation with electronic loyalty
- H3: Trust has a positive correlation with electronic loyalty
- H4: Experience has a positive correlation with electronic loyalty
- H5: Platform design is positively correlated with electronic loyalty

3.1. Research Design Architecture

4. Data Analysis

This data set is a survey of consumer loyalty on the 5G Medical website. We designed the Likert seven-point scale as a survey. We have investigated and analyzed the variables related to the value, belief, trust, experience, platform design, and electronic loyalty of an APP station. We distributed

a total of 174 online questionnaires and 297 interviews on the questionnaires, and a total of 471 were combined.

4.1. Analysis Results

There are 24 variables, the minimum number of samples is $24 \times 10 = 240$, and the number of significant samples is 464, which is much higher than the minimum number of samples.

More than 50% of P-value is less than 0.05, and the overall and individual MSA are greater than 0.5, so it is suitable for factor analysis.

5. Conclusions and Discussion

The biggest contribution of this research is to fill the research on the loyalty of 5G medical monitoring system for consumer electronics. In recent years, few scholars have studied the research on electronic loyalty of its related 5G medical monitoring system. The biggest limitation of this study is that it only targets the Chinese mainland market. This is a new concept and a new business model. If consumers can be included in different countries in the future, the direction of investigation will be different. The following points are my suggestions for future researchers and I hope to help future researchers:

1. The object of the questionnaire is:

The main questionnaires issued in this study are for the Chinese mainland market as survey objects, and it is recommended that future researchers can expand to foreign countries. Such research will contribute to the greater value of the data survey of the entire medical monitoring system.

2. Research objects can distinguish between their different variables:

Our research is mainly aimed at the loyalty status of some mainland China medical monitoring systems. It is suggested that future researchers can investigate the status of their medical monitoring systems for different national consumer groups. The subdivision of variables will bring about differences in the results of their research. This is also a suggestion for subsequent researchers who can look at different variables from such dimensions.

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